

ATTENTION TO SPORTS DEVELOPMENT AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698767>

Abstract. *Currently, mutual competition between the countries of the world, the manifestation of strength is expressed in the demonstration of sports and intellectual opportunities. This article provides information about the legal foundations of the development of the sports sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan and reforms in the field of Physical Culture and sports in our country.*

Keywords: *sports, physical education, “sprouts of Hope”, “harmonious generation”, “Universiade”, “New Uzbekistan”, “strategy of action”, concept, Asian Games and championships, Olympic Games.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the education and upbringing of children has become an important issue at the level of Public Policy. For this reason, the development of physical education and sports in our country has been defined as an important task. In this regard, we witness that the work carried out in our republic is highly appreciated on the scale of Jahan.

If every step in the life of the growing younger generation, its good intentions, aspirations and actions are correctly directed from a pre-scientifically based, programmed pedagogical and psychological point of view, then, of course, there is no doubt about the training of mature specialists who can take an important place in society from them.

It consists in the study, analysis, development of methodologies and recommendations on a psychological scientific basis of the process of educating the perfect generation to be physically healthy and strong, the factors affecting this process. To do this, it is necessary to find a solution to the following tasks:

- To learn the psychological foundations of preparing the perfect generation for the process of physical education;
- To study the current state of psychological study of the process of physical education; views of the scholars of the past on the upbringing of a person as physically and mentally mature, harmonious;
- Development of methods for solving socio-psychological problems of educating the perfect generation as a physically and psychologically mature, harmonious person.

Physical education will be more effective if you study the process of physical education of the younger generation on a scientific basis and develop the psychological factors affecting it, ways, methods of psychological influence on the educational process.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Dear President Sh.M. Mirziyoev, “In order for our youth to become independent-thinking, high-intellectual and spiritual potential, and become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale, our country will be happy. and we will mobilize all the forces and

possibilities of our society” demands high-quality and effective organization of education, and education of students as independent-thinking individuals with high intellectual and spiritual potential is one of the urgent issues of today.

Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 No. 3031 “on measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports”, resolution of August 14, 2018 No. 3907 “on measures to educate young people as spiritual and physical perfection, to qualitatively raise the educational and educational system to a new level, The decree of January 24, 2020 PF-5924 “on measures for further improvement and popularization of Physical Culture and sports” and serves to carry out the tasks set out in the regulatory legal acts related to this area.

It should be noted that physical education is being conducted as a lesson in all types of educational institutions on the basis of the state education system. In addition to the lesson, Sports Club classes, various sports competitions are held, on the basis of which it is clear that physical perfection is a priority in terms of content and essence when preparing for a profession. For this reason, such prestigious multi-level sports competitions as “Umid nihollari”, “Barkamol avlod”, “Universiada”, which are directly related to the continuity of Education, have become a tradition. One of the most important aspects is that presidential decrees and government decisions related to the development of children's sports are seriously increasing among young students to popularize sports, choose talented children, conduct tests and experiments, educate them as mature athletes. It is made clear that in the future they will defend the honor of our country at international sports competitions and bring it to even higher heights.

ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Currently, the mutual competition between the countries of the world, the manifestation of power, is expressed in the demonstration of sports and intellectual opportunities. The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.As Karimov noted: “Sport is an ambassador of peace. Our goal is also peace, tranquility and, on this basis, cooperation with the people of the world.

Nothing can make the country world famous as quickly as sports. Indeed, the international prestige of Uzbekistan is growing for the prizes won by the athletes of our country, participating with success at the Central Asian and Asian Games, various international tournaments, the World Championship and the Olympic Games. These achievements in sports cause the growth of feelings of self-awareness, solidarity and patriotism of our people.

The next four years in the Republic of Uzbekistan are a period of radical changes and rapid development in terms of quality without any exaggeration for our country and people. All regions of our country have become an unprecedented construction site - modern enterprises based on the latest technologies, excellent accommodation, spacious and smooth streets with all the amenities are being built.

The life of our people is radically improved, human rights and freedoms, the rule of law and social justice are decided. As a result of these changes and updates to the world, the expression “New Uzbekistan” was put into circulation as a recognition that our country is seriously changing for the better. Over the past four years, the practice of specific programs in the field of Physical Culture and sports that contribute to the strengthening of the health of the population, the widespread involvement of young people in sports, the formation of national teams with skilled athletes who ensure high results in sports and the creation of additional conditions for trainers, in order to form a comprehensive mature and physically healthy generation with a high culture in the

country, the following new regulatory legal acts have been adopted over the past four years in the field of Physical Culture and sports, including:

- Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. 4947 PF “on the strategy of actions in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021,
- Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3031 “on measures for the further development of Physical Culture and mass sports” on June 3, 2017,
- Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to further improve the activities of the State University of Physical Culture and sports of Uzbekistan” PP-3197 on August 10, 2017,
- On March 5, 2018, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5368 PF “on choratadbirs of radical improvement of the system of Public Administration in the field of Physical Culture and sports,
- Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3583 “on the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Physical Culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated March 5, 2018,
- On October 25, 2018, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 864 “on further improvement of the system of sports competitions of the Republic held between student and student youth,
- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 118 “on approval of the concept of development of Physical Culture and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2019-2023 “ on February 13, 2019,
- Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5924 “on measures to further improve and popularize Physical Culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated January 24, 2020,
- The concept of “development of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025” was adopted.

The adoption and implementation of the new normative legal acts on the field of physical education and sports adopted above are necessary conditions for regular physical education and sports for all layers of the country's population, especially the young generation. to create conditions, to strengthen the confidence of young people in their own will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, to develop feelings of bravery, patriotism, loyalty to the motherland, to participate in the Olympic Games, world championships, Asian Games and championships and other prestigious international competitions, large-scale works aimed at further raising the reputation of Uzbekistan in the world, further development of physical culture and sports are being carried out, opening the door to great opportunities for every citizen of our country

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the attention paid to physical culture and sports in New Uzbekistan today, the conditions created for our youth to regularly engage in physical education and sports, all this serves to ensure that our youth grow up spiritually mature, physically healthy, do not succumb to all kinds of foreign ideas, and, moreover, rise above the Uzbek flag in the world. In his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 29th anniversary of the state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that the foundation for a new renaissance - the third Renaissance-is being created in Uzbekistan at the

present time, when the glorious power of our people has moved. The fact that the third renaissance in Uzbekistan is also aimed at raising Physical Culture and sports is explained by the fact that the goal is to increase this “vital ability”.

It is no coincidence that our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev also emphasized that “we attach great importance to the rapid development of Sports, the promotion and application of athletes who have achieved high results in international competitions.”.

On March 19, 2019, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. The second of the 5 most important initiatives proposed by Mirziyoyev to establish work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres in our country on the basis of a new system is a practical proof of this by the fact that the latter are aimed at creating the necessary conditions for physical chanting of young people, their ability to show in the field of sports. This is the basis for the fact that in society it is decided to lead a healthy lifestyle - physical activity, exercise in the body, regular sports.

There is no doubt that the athletes of” new Uzbekistan “ will make their worthy contribution to the creation of the foundation for the third renaissance in our country. The above indicates that at the same time” New Uzbekistan “ has become one of the priorities at the level of public policy in the field of Physical Culture and sports, and a new stage has begun in this area.

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